

CENTRIFUGAL INFILTRATION OF PREFORMS BY MOLTEN ALUMINUM ALLOYS
TO FORM ALUMINUM-CARBON COMPOSITE

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ABSTRACT

Both theoretical and experimental research has been conducted on centrifugal infiltration of carbon fiber preforms by aluminum alloys to form tubular structures. Specifically, theoretical work has been done to derive the optimum chemistry, design and surface treatment of the fiber preform and infiltration conditions. Carefully designed experiments have been conducted to centrifugally infiltrate carbon fiber preforms with selected aluminum alloy. The cast composite tube was then examined using optical and scanning electron microscopy to check fiber distribution, infiltration efficiency, porosity and bonding. The variables considered included preform geometry, melt composition, temperature of the melt and the mold and atmosphere around the preform.

Key Word: Fiber-carbon, Filament-wound, matrix-aluminum, centrifugal casting, primary structures.

INTRODUCTION

Interest in aluminum-graphite continuous fiber composites date from about 1974 when the potentials of using high strength and modulus graphite fiber in metal matrices were determined. Since then tremendous progress has been made to develop this composite for several applications. Researchers, scientists and engineers have tried a variety of methods to produce this composite; one approach is that of liquid metal infiltration of graphite preforms.

Within this broad category of liquid infiltration, several techniques of infiltration are possible, namely, pressure infiltration, squeeze infiltration, centrifugal infiltration, etc. Most infiltration techniques use pressure to obtain good infiltration by taking advantage of the capillary effect. In this work only centrifugal infiltration was considered.

The properties of the composite are determined by the bonding between the metal matrix and graphite fiber. Good bonding infers a chemical bond of only a few angstroms so as not to degrade the fiber. A 100% mechanical bond is not desirable due to the poor load transfer that results.

The first part of this study entails a theoretical study including literature search (wetting, solidification, fiber orientation and material selection), design of equipment and standardization of experimental parameters. The second part includes production of casting using a standardized procedure and the third and final part includes the presentation of the results and an analysis of the findings.

No mechanical properties were determined, however, the structural characteristics of the castings suggested the effects on properties. The nucleation and growth of the solid from the liquid or graphite phase, matrix precipitate formation in the presence of fibers, solid-liquid interface characteristics, eutectic morphology, solidification cooling rate effects on wetting, etc., need to be studied to obtain a good understanding of the composite.

THEORETICAL CONSIDERATIONS

The theoretical criteria can be divided into six categories:

- A. Capillary Effects
- B. Interfacial Reactions
- C. Solidification
- D. Fiber Orientation
- E. Material Selection
- F. Standardization of experimental parameters and experimental design

A. Capillary Effects

The pressure differential between a liquid bath and the inside of the capillary is the consequence of surface energies of the liquid given by Young's equation, [1] where, ϕ = contact angle, r = curvature of liquid front, γ_{lv} = surface energy between liquid and vapor.

$$P_c = \frac{4 \cos \phi}{r} \gamma_{lv}$$

In the case of continuous fiber preforms which are filament wound, the interfiber spacing can be assumed to be the curvature of the liquid front (i.e. $r = 15 \mu\text{m}$). The surface energy of molten aluminum at different temperatures is given in Table I [2]. It can be seen that magnesium and increasing temperature decrease the surface energy. The relationship given in equation 1 becomes complex depending upon the wettability of the system i.e., when the system is non-wetting, a decrease in surface energy (γ_{lv}) will increase non-wettability and vice-versa when the system is wettable. This is due to $\cos \phi$ being negative when $\phi > 90^\circ$.

In consideration of this, a literature search was performed to obtain contact angle values for the Al-C (gr) system. It is apparent from Table II that none of the system reported had contact angles less than 90° which means that Al-C (gr) system is a non-wettable system. The system being non-wettable increases the problem of infiltration, as centrifugal pressure would act against wetting, increasing the wetting angle to greater than 90° .

Increasing temperature and time at temperature aids in decreasing contact angles. Figure 1 [3], shows that the contact angle decreases as the temperature increases. However, it was reported that this decrease in contact angle was due to the formation of Al_4C_3 (aluminum carbide). This aluminum carbide decreases the fiber properties due to the degradation of the fiber. Although the data was for the vitreous carbon-aluminum system, Table III, the trend noticed in the crystalline graphite-aluminum system could be applied e.g. temperature and time at temperature.

B. Interfacial Reactions

At very high temperatures ($>1060\text{K}$, 787°C), carbon from the graphite reacts with aluminum to form aluminum carbide. The reaction is :

This reaction degrades the fiber because the graphite crystallinity is decreased. Thus to maintain fiber properties, a coating needs to be applied such that the aluminum matrix would react only with the coating and form an intermetallic phase between the fiber and matrix (i.e. at the fiber-matrix interface).

Coatings on the graphite fiber have been used to increase wettability, interfacial reactions and to maintain fiber properties. A summary of the coating types and techniques studied in the literature is presented in Table IV. Most coatings and processes are not air stable except for

processes 1,3 and 8.

Process 1 in Table IV which is the silica coating, would not give a good bond due to silica not forming an intermetallic phase with aluminum (e.g. aluminum silicate) at temperatures less than 1060K (787°C),

This however would not hold true with magnesium as the reaction product is magnesium silicate. The problems of process 3 have already been discussed. Process 8, which has nickel or copper coating on the graphite fiber, is air stable and commercially available. The interfacial reactions between the nickel and aluminum can form an intermetallic phase like Al_3Ni . The fiber property degradation due to the coating has been reported to be less than 2%. Thus, fiber property is maintained, a favorable interfacial reaction takes place and the wetting contact angle is decreased by this nickel coated graphite fiber. However, the density of the system is increased by nickel.

C. Solidification

Solidification of the aluminum alloy around the fiber must take place over a minimum freezing temperature range due to the phenomenon of fiber pushing (particle pushing) in front of the solid-liquid interface. Further, the aluminum alloy must have good fluidity, a low melting point and low surface tension [16,17].

The fluidity of the aluminum alloy is a strong function of silicon content and molten metal temperature. F. R. Mollard et. al. [18] have reported that as the eutectic composition, is approached there is an increase in fluidity in aluminum alloys. This results in the selection of eutectic alloys where good fluidity, a low melting point, a narrow freezing range and low surface energies are obtained.

D. Fiber Orientation

The centrifugal infiltration of filament wound graphite preforms for mostly structural applications must consider the fact that different fiber helix angles result in different moduli, strength and thermal expansion coefficients. Most graphite fibers have two property directions (thermal expansion coefficients) i.e. longitudinal and transverse. The change in composite properties is due to the great difference in transverse and longitudinal properties of the graphite fiber. Several computer programs are available to estimate composite properties at different helix angles. The GENLAM [20] program was used for this paper. Table V presents a summary of anticipated directional properties for different helix angles.

D. Material Selection

On the basis of the above noted findings, the following were selected:

1. Matrix alloy = Aluminum A132 Alloy
2. Graphite Fiber = Nickel coated PAN T300 Fiber

The properties of the matrix alloy and graphite fiber are given in Table VI and were used the GENLAM program to obtain an optimized helix angle. The optimized properties were obtained at +16,-16 ply angle to the horizontal at 48 v/0 fiber Table V.

F. Standardization of Experimental Parameters and Experimental Design

The experimental parameters included temperature, time at temperature, solidification cooling rate, RPM, type of mold, design of mold and atmosphere. From the discussions given in previous sections and based on experience the following experimental parameters were selected:

1. Molten metal temperature = 1060K (787°C)
2. Time at temperature = 10 minutes
3. Solidification cooling rate = water cooled graphite mold (200°C/min)
4. Rotational Speed = 100 to 150 G force
5. Type of mold = Extra fine grain graphite mold
6. Atmosphere = Nitrogen

The graphite mold was selected for its good thermal conductivity and very low thermal expansion. A schematic diagram of the experimental set-up is given in Fig.2 . The procedure for producing the composite was formalized as : cast aluminum alloy tube, filament wound on the cast aluminum alloy tube and infiltrate the filament wound graphite fiber with the cast Al alloy.

ANALYSIS OF NICKEL COATED GRAPHITE FIBER

The properties of the nickel coated PAN graphite fiber and uncoated PAN fiber as reported by CYANAMID Company is given :

	PAN	Ni-Coated PAN
Fiber diameter (μm)	7	8
Coating thickness (μm)	-	0.5
Density (gm/cm^3)	.74	2.5 to 3.0
Tensile Strength MPa	3450	3105
Tensile Modulus GPa	239	234.6

Scanning electron microscopy was performed on the nickel coated graphite fiber and a photo micrograph is presented in Fig. 3. The nickel coating is uniform and ranges from 0.23 to 0.35 μm around the graphite fiber. From Fig. 3 the void volume was approximated. The final volume percent achievable would be aluminum matrix = 50.59%, graphite fiber = 41.25% and Ni = 8.16%.

As the nickel percentage in the fiber is high, the ideal situation for nickel dissolving in aluminum alloy would be 10-15% nickel and 90-85% aluminum alloy. Such a bond zone reaction will be critical to obtaining optimum composite properties. This can be achieved by control of melt super heat. Melt superheat was preferable because controls can be easier, further, after allowing adequate time, rapid cooling can reduce solid state diffusion.

EXPERIMENTS

Two castings were produced using the following parameters :

1. Molten Metal Temperature = 1060K (787°C)
2. Time at Temperature = 13 minutes
3. Rotational Speed = 1500 RPM
4. Nitrogen Atmosphere

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results of these experiments will be discussed as follows :

- A. Optical Macroscopy and Microscopy
- B. Scanning Electron Microscopy
- C. Density
- D. Mechanical Properties

A. Optical Macroscopy and Microscopy

Both castings resulted in good microscopic wetting and macroscopic wetting. The outside diameter of the casting contained some exposed fibers, attributed to the size of the casting and mold diameter. The gap between the fiber preform and mold was 1.6 mm which was mostly occupied by the mold wash. Hence full infiltration could not be obtained. This problem was not due to poor wetting but due to design. Figure 4 shows a macrophotograph of the as cast outside diameter surface in which some fibers are exposed. Figure 5 shows the macrophotograph of the cross section of the tube and no laminations are seen indicating good infiltration.

The as cast optical microstructures are shown in Fig. 6. It was observed that the moisture (water) from the polishing degraded the fiber which is apparent by the black precipitates around the fiber. It can be seen from these microstructures that there is good wetting of fibers and uneven interfiber spacing. The fibers have been dislodged from their original position due to either solidification, mold vibration or centrifugal force. The density difference between the fiber and matrix alloy is 0.05 gms/cm^3 at the start, but as the nickel from the graphite fiber dissolves, the density difference increases to a maximum of 1.2 gms/cm^3 . This large a density difference pushes the graphite fiber towards the center due to the centrifugal force. Hence, the graphite fiber if not held in position would have a tendency to move towards the inside diameter. This has dislodged the fiber causing the large variation in interfiber spacing.

Figure 7 show as cast optical microstructures after polishing in kerosene. The good wetting and disappearance of the black precipitates around the graphite fibers is evident. The optical microstructures show no segregation of phases as the eutectic (Al-Si), Al_3Ni and Al-Cu-Mg precipitates [21] have grown coherently besides the fiber indicating a sufficiently fast cooling rate.

B. Scanning Electron Microscopy Results

Figure 8 show scanning electron microphotographs of the as cast composite. The precipitate growth has taken place coherently. The identification of different precipitates was conducted in the SEM using spot x-ray spectrum analysis on the fiber-matrix interface indicating that Mg, Al, Si and Ni concentration at the interface were high.

C. Density

The density of the composite was determined by the determination of change of weight technique. Samples of the composite were weighed to four significant figures in air. They were then carefully weighed in water and the change in weight gave the density. The density of the composite determined by this method was 2.68 gms/cm^3 . This technique of density determination was derived from ASTM D792 (22). This ASTM standard, though written for solid plastics, could be applied for metal matrix composites.

D. Mechanical Properties

Tensile bars (flat bars) were made for property determination. The first two bars failed in the grip area due to the grips. The third bar was machined differently so as to obtain a good test. The strength obtained was $\sim 56.6 \text{ MPa}$, well below the anticipated strength. This low strength is attributed to poor material structures in the as-cast condition. Further, study of the fracture surface showed that fracture took place at a fiber depleted zone, indicating inhomogeneous distribution of graphite fibers in the matrix. This inhomogeneity was caused due to fiber movement during casting and a density decrease in fibers. Fiber constraint is therefore very essential. Figure 9 shows the scanning electron fractographs. The inhomogeneous distribution is well evident. However, the good wetting of the graphite fiber with the matrix aluminum alloy can be authenticated from the fractographs.

CONCLUSIONS

1. Centrifugal infiltration of graphite fibers shows good wetting of the fibers with the Al matrix.
2. Temperature and time at temperature are a function of wetting and have been optimized to be 1060K (787°C) and 10 minutes respectively, for the present process of infiltration.
3. The difference in density between graphite fiber and aluminum matrix tends to force the graphite fibers towards the inside diameter.
4. The property of the composite is determined by fiber distribution, amount of degradation, casting defects and matrix precipitate homogeneity.

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Table I: Surface Energies of Liquid Aluminum Alloys at Different Temperatures

Table II: Contact Angles in Al Alloys on Graphite

Temperature		Alloy	Surface Energies		Alloy element	Composition %wt	Atmosphere	Contact Angles degrees
°C	°F		$\gamma_{LV}(\text{mJ/m}^2)$					
700	1292	Al-2% Si	847	C	1.62	Vacuum	134	
800	1472		836		5.04		132	
900	1652		826		9.82		10-5 Torr	127
700	1292	Al-2% Mg	767	Mg	1.39	Helium	145	
800	1472		757		4.52		131	
900	1652		747		9.98		115	
700	1292	Al-2% Cu	843	Si	2.58	Vacuum	146	
800	1472		832		0.94		Vacuum	>130
900	1652		822		0.90		10-5 Torr	>130
700	1292	Pure Al	851	Mn	1.24		>130	
800	1472		840					
900	1652		830					

Table III : Contact Angles of Aluminum Alloys on Vitreous Carbon Substrates

Alloy Composition	Time Held at Temp. (min)	Atmosphere	Contact Angles at Temp. °C			
			700	800	900	1000
Al Pur	30	10-6 Torr	160	140	102	77
	30	Argon	160	150	140	110
	100	10-6 Torr	140	125	102	65
Al-Ti 0.1	30	10-6 Torr	135	127	95	68
Al-Si 19	30	10-6 Torr	154	124	90	58
Al-Be 0.8	30	10-6 Torr	~170	~170	~170	~170
Al-Ca 11	15	Argon	87	77	-	-
Al-Li 6	15	Argon	~29 at 640 C			

Table IV : Summary of Coating Type and Technique Used by Several Authors

Type of Coating	Technique	Reference
1.Silica	Metal alkoxide reaction (air stable)	4,8,9,10,11
2.Sodium, Titanium, Tin & Copper-Tin-Titanium	Sodium Bath Process (not air stable)	5,6,7
3.Al ₄ C ₃	High Temp. Reaction (air stable)	3
4.Titanium Boron Coating Process	Chemical vapor deposition of TiCl ₄ and BCl ₃ reactants (not air stable)	5
5.Aluminum	CVD of triisobutly Al (commercially unavailable)	12
6.Aluminum	Physical spraying using plasma gun (not commercially available)	13
7.Amorphous	Radio Frequency Plasma assisted CVD (not commercially available)	14
8.Nickel and Elements	Electrodeposition (air stable and commercially available)	15

Table V : Theoretical properties of Al A132 alloy - Ni - Coated T300 fiber composite

Vol%	Cross Ply Angle	E GPa	Longitudinal CTE x10 ⁻⁶ 1/°C	Transverse CTE x10 ⁻⁶ 1/°C
48	0	138.5	-0.747	0.7
	16	124.4	-0.743	0.39
	45	64.7	-0.482	-0.48
	60	41.9	-0.090	-0.68
	75	29.1	0.424	-0.745
	90	25.1	0.7	-0.747

Table VI : Aluminum A132 Alloy and Ni-Coated T300 Fiber Properties

Material	T.S. MPA	Y.S. MPA	Modulus GPA	Coefficient of Thermal Expansion 1/°Cx10 ⁻⁶		Composition
				Longitudinal	Transverse	
Al A132-T65	193	248	73	21.78	21.78	12.0 Si, 0.8 Cu, 1.2Mg, 2.5 Ni bal Al, Melting range =537 to 565°C
NiCoated PAN	-	3102	234	-1.2	16.2	-

Fig. 1 : Contact angle as a function of temperature for aluminum - vitreous carbon system.

Fig. 2 : Schematic diagram illustrating the experimental set-up (not to scale) used in the Al-Graphite composite casting.

Fig. 3 : Scanning electron microphotograph of nickel coated T300 graphite fiber showing uniform coating of 0.5 μm thick coating around the fiber.

Fig. 4 : Photograph of the Al A132 alloy - Graphite fiber casting. Fiber exposure is visible in the outside diameter. This is not due to poor infiltration but due to design.

Fig. 5 : Photograph of the cross section of the composite. No laminations are visible indication good infiltration and not engulfment.

Fig. 6 : As-cast unetched microphotograph of the composite. This photo shows the eutectic Si particles (dark grey), Mg_2Si particles (black precipitate in matrix) and Al-Cu-Ni (thick light outline) particles. The Ni coating on the fiber has dissolved in the Al matrix. Coherent growth of all precipitates has taken place at inter-fiber locations and no drastic segregation of these precipitates away from the fiber is observed. Fiber degradation evident from the black precipitates around the fiber is recognised to be from the metallographic preparation ie using water as a lubricant during polishing. Interfiber distance variation was considerable due to fiber movement and fiber density loss during solidification.

Fig. 7 : As-cast unetched microphotograph of the composite after polishing in kerosene. Black precipitates around fiber noticed after polishing using water as a lubricant is not present in this microphotograph. The precipitates as mentioned in Fig. 6 can be recognised.

Fig. 8 : Scanning electron microphotograph of as-cast etched piece. Precipitate growth has not taken place preferentially. The matrix gap between the left and right is from the different ply's in the composite. Interfiber distance variation is quite considerable and fiber constriction seems to be necessary to prevent fiber movement during solidification.

Fig. 9 : Scanning electron fractograph of the composite. The fracture shows that cleavage has taken place in a transprecipitate manner. Fiber presence is not noticeable indicating the fracture has taken place at fiber depleted regions, further implying inhomogeneous distribution of fiber in the matrix.